

Paternalism and Autonomi:

Introduction:

Paternalism and its opposition to autonomy are essential topics in professional ethics and applied ethics that philosophers have written extensively about. In this essay, I will discuss the definitions of these concepts and then try to show whether these two concepts can be combined or not. I will give some examples from health care that the paternalistic approach can be defensible and not necessarily in conflict with autonomy. However, before that, let us define the key concepts such as ethics, profession, professional ethics, paternalism, and autonomy. What do we mean when we talk about these concepts?

Ethics: ethics is about how we should act. It is related to how we should act or why it is right to act in specific ways. Often such problems are related to questions such as "what is right and wrong, good and evil?". An action can be assessed from several different ethical perspectives. These perspectives are often expressed in various ethical theories. Such theories can help us better grasp the problems associated with action and provide a reasoned solution to them (Henriksen & Vetlesen, 2011, 158-159). The most important normative ethical theories include: 1- deontological ethics 2- utilitarianism ethics 3- Virtue ethics 4- Empathy ethics 5- Discourse ethics. Perhaps we can say that no universal ethical theory is correct in all ways or that alone manages to capture all aspects of moral phenomena. It is possible to look at a phenomenon from several sides. (Henriksen & Vetlesen, 2011, 159). Ethics is, in short, the theoretical basis of morality (Christoffersen, 2019, 14).

Professional: profession has something to do with some different jobs which come with more education. A profession today is the same as a job one is skilled in. All professions work not only *for* people but also *with* people. For example, teachers relate to students, doctors to patients, lawyers to clients, etc. However, here, it is important to note that not all jobs are professions. It needs an academic education and that the person is qualified (Christoffersen, 2019, 16-19). This qualification confers certain privileges that others do not have. These privileges are there to help other people and benefit the community.

Professional ethic: In the book "*profesjonsetikk*", we read that Grimen defines professional ethics as a codex - understood as a set of more or less formalized norms and values - which is to safeguard the social mission of the profession in question (Christoffersen, 2019, 24). According to Nortvedt, the core of professional ethics is the professional practitioner's responsibility to benefit the patient and the client (Christoffersen, 2019, 24).

Paternalism: The word paternalism is derived from the adjective paternal, meaning "fatherly". Paternalism is an act that limits a person's or group's freedom or autonomy and is intended to promote their good. When parents forbid their children to drink too much alcohol, or when parents forbid their children to smoke, when hiding away drugs from a friend or spouse with drugs problems, or the state requires the use of seat belts and motorcycle helmets, these are the rules and actions paternalistic (Nortvedt, 2008. 251). Therefore, paternalism is acting for the good of others without their consent, as a father does for his children. In the political sense of paternalism, the state, like the father of society, prevents people from harming themselves.

Autonomy: is the capacity to make an informed, uncoerced decision. Autonomy is being independent or self-governing. Personal autonomy is the capacity to decide for oneself and pursue a course of action in one's life, often regardless of any particular moral content (Dryden, Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy). Autonomy can be understood as a right individuals should have by their decision-making ability as rational persons (Nortvedt, 2008. 252).

Paternalism and Autonomi:

One of the most central questions in professional ethics concerns paternalism, which applies to what extent can people's freedom of action be legitimately restricted by reference to their own best interests? The professional, ethical paternalism question is how to act to achieve clients' best interests while respecting their autonomy and freedom? (Nortvedt, 2008. 251) Can people or clients know what is best for them? According to Thomas. H. Marshal, the British sociologist, argues that the client cannot always assess his needs (Fauske, 2008. 33). So, what are the arguments to defend paternalism? Furthermore, what are the arguments for rejecting paternalism? Are there any syntheses to combine paternalism and autonomy? We will look at why individuals do not know what is best for them concerning assessment competence.

As noted, paternalism is behavior by an individual, organization, or government to restrict the freedom or independence of an individual or group regarding their interest. For example, banning a person from swimming on dangerous beaches without the presence of a lifeguard or banning the use of drugs. In fact, with the help of the paternalism approach, the government seeks society's public interest. However, can individuals not recognize their interests? Is not man a rational and autonomous being? Why does he need external authority to discern what is good to him? Stuart Mill believes that restrictions on freedom can only be justified when the intention is to prevent harm to others (Nortvedt, 2008. 252). This statement

is understandable; nobody has the right to harass other people. But what about people who want to hurt themselves? Or in other cases, they stop their treatment and are not willing to take, for example, the medicine prescribed by their doctor, which can be life dangerous for them if they don't take the treatment. Is there a need for coercion here so that the patient does not harm himself? What's the solution? In the practice of a profession, it can be when a patient or client refuses treatment or a measure that will positively have significant health or welfare consequences for the person (Nortvedt, 2008. 255).

According to Stuart Mill, no one has the right to use force against anyone even if they want to do him good. If someone tries to commit suicide and throws herself from the mountain, you have no right to force them to stop. One cannot force a person to do anything; a person has absolute freedom without limit unless that person will harm others. Mill believes that the most important moral principle is the "harm principle" (do not harm others). The government and society can intervene in the behavior of individuals only when the "principle of harm" is endangered. Mill also believes that the good of society or community health will not be sufficient justification for government intervention. However, if someone is going to hurt other people physically, then the issue goes beyond the realm of freedom. Thus, coercion (paternalism) can be introduced here (Eunseong Oh, 2016, 1-2). This view of Mill can be referred to as "soft paternalism".

In most societies, we see laws that are all paternalistic. These laws are so customary today that rarely do we see these laws in conflict with autonomy. For example, laws that prevent people from harming themselves or rules such as banning brothels and buying certain drugs only with a doctor's prescription or using a seat belt when driving a car, etc. These laws indicate that the government seeks to protect the human body and restricts behaviors to maintain human physical health.

Why is it important to protect the physical and mental health of people? This question falls within the realm of ethics. Proponents of paternalism believe that interfering with a person's rights and freedoms is essential to supporting their moral upbringing. Perhaps we can say that a series of constraints are created for the greater good and better results regarding utilitarianism. However, from another perspective, of course, these rules can also have some negative consequences. Acceptance of the paternalistic approach leads to the criminalization of certain behaviors. Today, many people are sent to prison for crimes such as sex, alcohol, drugs, gambling, and other crimes based on paternalism in some countries. Are these laws that cause criminalization of specific behaviors that lead to the increase of criminals in society in line with the public interest and the health of society? The same paternalistic rules can also

create a stigma against these people and may have other side effects. Critics of paternalism also see this as at odds with human freedom and autonomy. One of the people who criticize paternalism is the German philosopher Emmanuel Kant.

Paternalism can conflict with self-autonomy because the authority or professions reduces the freedom of will of people. Not everyone knows what is best for them, or many people do not have the judgment to do so. With a critical view of paternalism, the authority considers the person ignorant of his destiny, happiness, and best interests and thus considers the control over the person. Virtue and value appear when a person acts freely; that is why Kant considers man as an end and not a means (Christoffersen, 2019, 45). Therefore, any attempt to restrict human freedom and decide on their place denies human dignity and rejects human values. In other words, paternalism is the development of people's interests in life and health at the expense of their freedom. Freedom is causing humans to grow and find their perfection, and it is wrong to think that man can grow morally by force and coercion. Kant believes that the rulers who look at other people who lack judgment consider themselves fathers and guardians of people, and therefore Kant believes "paternalism is the greatest conceivable despotism." (Rosen, 1996, 176). Paternalistic government, no matter how well-intentioned and rational, ultimately tends to view that most people do not have the ability to make the right choices. In other words, in practice, they want to say that these people will never reach the stage of growth. The consequence of this is an insult to our rational choice. These are some criticisms that can be made against paternalism.

However, the critical point is, Kant did not talk about healthcare or patients who do not have the decision-making competence. Kant's argument against paternalism is very general and may not be practical in professions. In practice, many have experienced those the client's rights are not adequately secured if only rules and principles on autonomy and self-determination are referred to. The rules become too abstract and do not always correspond to the specific needs that specific clients and patients actually have. When self-determination and autonomy are made to the highest value, there is a danger that those who are not self-determining and autonomous will not receive the help they need and are entitled to (Christoffersen, 2019, 45).

Another point is, it is true that man was created free and is free in his actions and deeds. Nevertheless, his freedom is not "absolute" but limited and conditional based on the "harm principle," the idea I mentioned earlier, which Stuart Mill brings in the discussion. Perhaps it can be said that absolute freedom is anarchy. That is, every human being can do anything, and there are no laws to restrict human behavior. *Absolute freedom* is an argument

advocated by anarchist philosophers such as Mikhail Bakunin. In addition, there are other restrictions. In fact, "social laws" are a violation of human freedom. Every law is a kind of restriction. That is why the issue of "justice and freedom" has always been a kind of dichotomy against each other. So is it correct to say that any social law is a form of coercion, and consequently, paternalism is inevitable in law-abiding societies? Man is free to exercise and run and walk in nature, but does he have the right to jump off a mountain and commit suicide? Paternalists say he does not have this right and freedom to commit suicide. Precisely as the harm principle against others is essential, this principle also applies to the individual himself: they don't have the right to harm themselves. On the other hand, some social realities, for instance, people with mental illness, drug issues, and dementia who don't have the good decision-making competence and do not have the necessary qualifications to recognize their goods, the necessity of resorting to paternalistic principles is arguably defensible.

An important distinction is between "soft" and "hard" paternalism. Soft paternalism means that restrictions on freedom are justified because the person is not competent to make well-informed choices. On the other hand, hard paternalism is actions that restrict a person's freedom of action and choice, even if the person is able to make independent choices (Nortvedt, 2008.253). However, the question is, what are the characteristics of a good decision-making person (beslutningkompetanse)? Are there degrees and levels of decision-making skills? Can this competence reduce or increase in time? Can a person be in decision-making in some areas but not in others? Questions about decision-making competence are essential because we know whether paternalistic interventions can be legitimate if we know which person has decision-making competence. If a person is competent to make decisions, paternalistic interventions to protect the person against their actions cannot be justified (Nortvedt, 2008. 253).

The rationale for paternalism is that the person no longer has such self-determination and instead has no insight into his own best interests. The person is therefore served by others entering the situation and taking control, making decisions. The ethical rationale for paternalism, is always the consideration of the person's good. The interpretation of what is in the person's best interests requires experience-based insight combined with empathy and listening to colleagues' advice and recommendations (Henriksen & Vetlesen, 2011, 225). According to Nortvedt, it is common to say that decision-making competence is one of the most essential characteristics of a person's autonomy (Nortverdt, 2008. 253). There are usually four prerequisites for a person to be said to be competent in decision-making:

1. The person must have the necessary and relevant information

2. the person must be able to process the information
3. The person must have the necessary insight into what the information means for any action choices
4. the person must be able to express their preferences adequately. (Nortvedt, 2008. 253).

However, these criteria are not easy to assess. Simply because they are pretty general and because they can be challenging to assess in each personal case. Knowing the client's preferences can be challenging if the professional does not know the client before. Another problem is that the client's preferences are not stable over time, so the person's preferences can change over time (nortvedt, 2008. 253- 254). For example, in medical treatment, patients' preferences can often depend on the development of the disease and the disease phase the person is in (nortvedt, 2008. 254).

The third problem is that decision-making competence can vary concerning circumstances and situations. A person's decision can be the result of short-term confusion, psychological crisis, etc. The fourth problem and question are whether one can talk about a partial decision-making competence? So that the person has the competence to make some assessments, but not others? In such a case, however, it is a matter of strengthening the client's / patient's competence in the professional field through information and independence (nortvedt, 2008. 254).

Cooperation with the patient should be based on mutual trust and should, where possible, be based on informed consent (Christoffersen, 2019, 39). Nevertheless, we should be borne in mind that some patients do not have this ability and information. Some patients are unable to speak and make decisions and need first aid. A situation where the patient cannot assess their needs, such as dementia or even those with acute mental illness or severe drug addiction, needs an external authority to help them in these difficult situations where they cannot make decisions and may not know what is good for them. For example, a demented person who has defecated and needs to be cleaned, if this person confronts, here the nurse can use coercion for the good of patient's health. The professional must take into account the patient's needs. If a person is not decision-making, paternalistic actions may seem legitimate. What about patients who do not accept treatment and refuse to take medicine for their good? This poses a moral dilemma for professionals: respecting or acting contrary to the patient's will? Hard paternalists respond that one must perform coercion and disqualify a person's autonomous decision because patients do not have the judgment to know what is best for them. The consequence of such paternalism is that the individual's autonomy is violated, not

least the personal goals and interests the individual himself considers crucial to him (Nortvedt, 2008. 255).

In Norway, coercion can be used for acute mental patients and drug abuse people who can harm themselves or others, and hard paternalism is strictly legal. Here coercion is posed because the patient can be dangerous to himself and other people. The force can be justified by the fact that the person is so firmly addicted to drugs that the person is not considered to be able to decide about treatment. A person addicted to drugs has less willpower, and the effect of drugs on the brain is scientifically proven. An addicted person may experience forgetfulness and violence and make wrong decisions or be weakened by addiction. Isn't there an ethical choice here that forced the person to help him and save him from this situation for his good? It should also be noted that a person who voluntarily comes to an addiction treatment institution intends to seek help from others and get rid of this situation. Authority is not evenly distributed between doctor and patient. On the contrary, the patient often comes to the doctor precisely because the doctor has power that the patient does not have and wants to put his problems in the doctor's hands (Christoffersen, 2019 39). But because his will (addicted person) is weak, he needs external authority and coercion to save him from addiction.

However, what about a mentally ill person who does not believe he/she is sick and acknowledges they have the power of discernment and decision-making competence? Should the patient be left alone in this situation? The problem is not simple. There is consensus and agreement among international medical ethics that patients who refuse health care and are competent to make decisions should have the right to do so, even if the choice can lead to severe consequences for the individual himself (Nortvedt, 2008. 255). A mentally ill person may harm others and engage in violent and dangerous behaviors. Should he be forcibly treated before these violent behaviors occur? Or should authority wait for irrational and violent behavior to occur and then impose force on treatment? If health care organizations were aware of the acute mental illness of a person who potentially can harm others and took action and applied strict hard paternalism for treatment, Breivik, for example, might not have killed nearly 90 young kids. Many of the violent behaviors of terrorists are due to mental illness. Of course, this is the most extreme example and may not be a good example. However, the question is whether medical organizations are allowed to use force to treat acute mental illness? If acute psychiatric patients were able to make the right choice, then they were not mentally ill. Because their mental illness is related to the mind, will, psyche; thus they don't have the decision-making competence as others do, they do not have the power to make

the right decision, and they may live in illusions, paranoia, and fears that lie within them. So they need help even if it is necessary to run hard paternalism.

Consequently, the hard paternalistic method can be used here to maintain the individual's health to avoid hurting his/her family and society. So in this view Paternalism is a necessary part of professional practice in those situations where the client can not look after his interests, especially in health care. Complicated cases are where the person is not competent to make decisions, and there is disagreement about what is in the patient's best interests (Nortvedt, 2008. 259).

Conclusion:

In conclusion, Liberal thinkers have always emphasized the need for individual freedom of choice as an inalienable human right and have condemned paternalistic approaches. However, as we have shown, any law restricts man to a part of liberties. There is no absolute freedom, and the "law" itself is a sign of paternalism. Consequently, the point is the boundary of the law and how much is the law allowed to restrict freedoms? If the purpose of the law is to improve society's life, welfare, and health, it is reasonable to deprive human beings of a series of freedoms to provide a better society. Absolute freedom can play a negative role. In the words of Thomas Hobbes, "Man is the wolf of man,; *Homo homini lupus*" and absolute freedom has the potential to create disorder and harm society. Man is free to choose his destiny, but he is not free to harm others. Man is free to go his own way, but he is not free to block the way of others. Man is free to choose the goal of his life, but can this goal be to the detriment of society and the moral decline of society? Can an anti-Semitic person say that my goal is to kill every Jew I come across? Undoubtedly not. Freedom must not conflict with the welfare and human rights, and citizenship rights of others. So paternalism is not necessarily at odds with freedom. Because we do not have absolute freedom. Isaiah Berlin, the British philosopher, speaks of two types of freedom, negative and positive, which is another topic that we do not need to detail now.

However, numerous studies and evidence show that human beings, in many cases, do not act according to the model of a rational man and therefore do not enjoy the potential benefits of freedom of choice (like Milgrim experiment, Stanford prison experiment, and Asch conformity experiment). Can it be argued that people's preferences are often vague and based on incomplete information, prejudice, and bias? Their choices are often misguided by

biases and false assumptions. I think some form of paternalism can be beneficial to society while pushing people towards welfare, that improve their well-being, and at the same time does not reduce their freedom. I think a type of soft paternalism is not in conflict with self-autonomy. According to this view, soft paternalism, will not reduce the choices of individuals and is not eliminated, restricted, or prohibited. If, for whatever reason, one wants to smoke, eat much chocolate, or leave no savings for one's retirement, no one is forced or restricted by policymakers to do otherwise. Such policymaking only flips the individual to choose the proper behavior, perhaps. Moreover, these paternalistic laws may have good personal and social benefits for them. I believe that the principle of paternalism does not mean ignoring one's autonomy. Just as parents may decide about their children to respect their interests, for example, the doctor may decide to respect the patient's interests. However, since it is assumed that human beings must freely choose their destiny, doctors in medical matters are obliged to provide their patients with the necessary information to make a decision. As a result, the issue of treatment should be based on the free and informed consent of the individual. Therefore, physicians have a moral obligation to pave the way for the patient to make informed decisions.

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